

Advanced NOMA-based RRM Schemes for Broadcasting in 5G mmWave Frequency Bands

Eneko Iradier, *Member, IEEE*, Aritz Abuin, *Graduate Student Member, IEEE*, Rufino Cabrera, *Graduate Student Member, IEEE*, Iñigo Bilbao, *Graduate Student Member, IEEE*, Jon Montalban, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Pablo Angueira, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Sunhyoung Kwon, *Member, IEEE*, Namho Hur, *Member, IEEE*, Sung-Ik Park, *Senior Member, IEEE*,

Abstract—A relevant solution for the high demand for new multimedia applications and services is millimeter wave (mmWave) frequency band in 5G. However, in order to face the technological challenges of the present and those that will appear in the short-term future, it is necessary to improve the spectral efficiency of 5G systems. In particular, the Radio Resource Management (RRM) module is considered an essential component. Nevertheless, resource allocation techniques that combine orthogonal multiplexing (OMA) schemes, such as Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA), with Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) techniques have not been studied in-depth. Therefore, this article designs and evaluates different RRM models that combine TDMA with NOMA for innovative applications in the 5G mmWave frequency bands. To this end, the advantages and challenges associated with mmWave frequency bands and potential future applications are introduced. An innovative use case has been designed to test the RRM models. The use case is based on the on-demand distribution of multimedia content in high-density environments, such as museum halls. The on-demand content aims at offering Augmented Reality (AR) services to unicast users in order to provide personalized services. The models have been evaluated in terms of throughput, capacity, and availability. According to the results, the combined RRM techniques offer up to 50% more capacity than the single multiplexing technology models and can provide video-on-demand service to practically the entire cell.

Index Terms—5G, AR, broadcast, LDM, millimeter frequency bands, mmWaves frequency bands, NOMA, personalization, resource allocation, RRM, unicast.

I. INTRODUCTION

Serving the constant evolution of multimedia services requested by users has become one of the most relevant challenges of today's wireless communication networks. The emergence of new applications such as Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) or the increase in the definition

of video services (4k/8k) has caused the data rate required by the end-user to grow exponentially during the last years. In fact, according to recent studies, around three-fourths of the data consumed in the world is expected to be video by the end of 2021 [1].

5G is expected to be the technology that leads the implementation of the most challenging and demanded use cases. In fact, the Radiocommunication Sector of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU-R) has divided the entire application frame into three use case families: enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC), and massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) [2]. Each of these three families has very different requirements, as defined in [3]. For example, eMBB, which is based on traditional multimedia delivery, requires around 10 Gbps of peak data rate values for the uplink and around 20 Gbps for the downlink. Moreover, high mobility rates have to be also supported (up to 500 km/h). Then, URLLC is oriented to mission-critical applications, where reliability (loss rates below 10^{-9}) and end-to-end latency (up to 1 ms) are the most critical Key Performance Indicators (KPI). Finally, mMTC is focused on covering extremely crowded networks, such as Internet of Things (IoT) or sensor networks. In this case, density rates above 10^6 devices per km^2 have to be guaranteed.

The first version of 5G New Radio (NR) [4] serves a broad set of applications with an increase in services robustness. This improvement is achieved with Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC) codes and better use of radio resources. Additionally, 5G implements a flexible physical layer (PHY) in which the parameters can be configured to suit the latency or capacity needs required by the application. Another relevant novelty is the possibility of using the millimeter wave (mmWave) frequency band, where bandwidths of hundreds of MHz can be allocated [5].

In addition to going up in frequency, an improvement in the spectral efficiency of 5G can facilitate the implementation of the most demanding use cases. In particular, Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) techniques have presented a very promising performance vs. complexity trade-off during the last years. In fact, an excellent example of the success of NOMA happened in 2016, when a low-complexity NOMA solution (Layered Division Multiplexing, LDM) was accepted to be part of the PHY of the latest Advanced Television Systems Committee (ATSC) standard [6]. NOMA solutions have also

This work has been partially supported by the Basque Government (the grant IT1234-19), by the Spanish Government (project PHANTOM under the grant RTI2018-099162-B-I00 (MCIU/AEI/FEDER, UE)) and by the Institute of Information & Communications Technology Planning & Evaluation (IITP) grant funded by the Korea government (MSIT) (No.2017-0-00081, Development of Transmission Technology for Ultra High Quality (UHQ)).

Eneko Iradier, Aritz Abuin, Rufino Cabrera, Iñigo Bilbao, Jon Montalban, and Pablo Angueira are with the Department of Communications Engineering, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Torres Quevedo 1, 48013 Bilbao, Spain (email: eneko.iradier@ehu.eus, aabuin003@ikasle.ehu.eus, rufinoreydel.cabrera@ehu.eus, inigo.bilbao@ehu.eus, jon.montalban@ehu.eus, pablo.anguera@ehu.eus).

Sunhyoung Kwon, Namho Hur and Sung-Ik Park are with the Media Research Division, Electronics and Telecommunications Research Institute, Daejeon 34129, South Korea (e-mail: shkwon@etri.re.kr; namho@etri.re.kr; psi76@etri.re.kr).

been proposed to be combined with broadband standards such as 4G [7] or 5G [8], based on the capacity advantage that they offered in comparison with traditional Time or Frequency Domain Multiplexing (TDM/FDM) solutions. However, recent studies have discovered that although the Radio Resource Management obtained with NOMA techniques outperforms TDM or FDM, it is still a non-optimal solution [9]. As opposed to TDM/FDM, NOMA solutions lack some degree of flexibility in Resource Block (RB) allocation. Therefore, the combination of NOMA and TDM/FDM techniques in the same RRM scheme could optimize the resource allocation issue.

This paper aims at analyzing the possible RRM schemes that combine NOMA and TDMA techniques for 5G mmWave frequency bands. The advantages and disadvantages of the implementation of 5G in mmWave frequency bands have to be studied. Then, different NOMA+TDMA RRM schemes have to be designed and evaluated under novel use cases oriented to potential applications for mmWave frequency bands. In summary, the technical contributions of this paper include:

- 1) Analysis of the challenges and benefits of using mmWave frequency bands in 5G, as well as a description of the potential applications.
- 2) Design of different RRM schemes that combine NOMA and TDM multiplexing.
- 3) Evaluation of the proposed RRM schemes under an innovative use case for future mmWave frequency band applications.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The next section describes the related works published up to now on this topic. Section III is focused on the overview of the impact of the mmWave frequency bands in 5G and the potential future applications. In Section IV, the proposed NOMA+TDMA RRM schemes are designed and detailed. Then, in Section V, a use case related with on-demand content distribution in high density environments is introduced, and Section VI presents the results obtained with the RRM schemes in the proposed use case based on different evaluation metrics. Finally, Section VII contains the conclusions.

II. RRM IN MMWAVE FREQUENCY BANDS: RELATED WORK

Milimeter wave band enables the use of significantly larger channel bandwidths than previous broadband standards. Therefore, the design of RRM algorithms that efficiently manage a large number of radio resources is crucial [10]. This section presents some of the most relevant studies in the literature related to RRM in the mmWave frequency bands.

One of the main concerns of the applications carried out in the mmWave frequency bands is to coordinate the access of different service requests. Authors of [11] evaluate the resource allocation strategy in mixed multicast/unicast traffic environments using queuing theory. A mathematical model is developed to optimize the 5G parameters. The authors define a set of parameters that considerably affect the unicast RRM management, such as the number of unicast requests or the arrival direction. Results indicate that the transmitter can predict the network density to provide full coverage of

a particular area. Another alternative to handle users/services with different characteristics is to use heterogeneous networks. In particular, in [12], the authors study the resource allocation in multiple heterogeneous networks in the mmWave frequency bands, where each band has specific propagation conditions. Two different access techniques are proposed: the single-band access scheme and the multi-band access scheme. The first approach is based on time fraction allocation, whereas the second is based on a Markov model framework. Results indicate that multi-band schemes outperform single-band solutions, especially when the network is in light load mode.

In addition to the networks implemented in the mmWave frequency bands, many applications will continue to be based on sub-6 GHz networks, mainly due to the lower path losses. Therefore, the correct coordination of both frequency bands and managing the resources dedicated to each of the bands is another of the RRM challenges. This issue is discussed in [13], where resource allocation techniques are studied inside a broader framework that considers also relay address, beam selection, and interference coordination. In this case, the sub-6 GHz band and the mmWave frequency band are used simultaneously with different objectives. While the first is used for control and reliable communications, the latter is used for high throughput applications. The authors evaluate the coordinated management of the multi-parameter framework in both frequency bands at the same time. Then, in [14], the authors propose a diverse network, where sub-6 GHz macrocells and mmWave frequency bands small cells co-exist. The study seeks an energy-efficient RRM algorithm using uplink NOMA in ultradense Internet of Things (UD-IoT) environments. Results indicate that the proposed algorithm outperforms the existing works.

Then, another relevant challenge of network design in mmWave frequency bands is the correct implementation and optimum use of the backhaul links. Concerning this challenge, in [15], the Radio Access (RA) and the backhaul (BH) are implemented in the same mmWave frequency band, and so, both services are unified in the same network. The authors present three dynamic RRM algorithms to manage the resource allocation between RA and BH for several pico stations together. Algorithms are oriented to enhance the network capacity and guarantee fairness among stations. The results indicate that the network capacity could be increased up to 35% when the proposed dynamic algorithms are used.

Finally, the RRM algorithms oriented to mmWave frequency bands have to be adapted to novel use cases, such as Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) applications. For example, in [16], the RRM performance is evaluated in downlink-UAV networks that implement antenna sectoring approaches. In this case, the goal is to maximize the network capacity while ensuring a minimum data rate to each user and limiting the transmission power.

Although several works have been presented in the literature about different RRM algorithms in mmWave frequency bands, the potential gain obtained by combining non-orthogonal techniques with orthogonal techniques, such as TDMA or FDMA, has not been studied. Furthermore, no work in the literature suggests combining orthogonal and non-orthogonal

RRM techniques to provide convergence between broadcast and unicast services. This work studies and evaluates different combined NOMA+TDMA RRM alternatives for a use case applicable in networks based on mmWave frequency bands.

III. 5G IN MMWAVE FREQUENCY BANDS

This section discusses the main implications of the implementation of 5G in mmWave frequency bands. Then, the propagation channel conditions, the potential gains and the description of the potential applications are presented.

A. Configuration

The 5G configuration is different in the millimeter frequency band and the sub-6GHz band [17]. Therefore, this subsection analyzes the main differences and their impact on the system.

Firstly, it should be noted that although technically the radioelectric spectrum defined as millimeter frequency band is between 30 GHz and 300 GHz (wavelengths between 10 mm and one mm), in the 5G ecosystem, mmWave frequency bands are understood as the frequencies above 6 GHz [18]. In particular, the frequency band reserved for mmWaves is defined as the Frequency Range 2 (FR2) and is comprised between 24.25 GHz and 52.6 GHz. According to the latest announcements from governments and world spectrum regulators, the first 5G in mmWave frequency bands systems are expected to be implemented in the 26 GHz (3GPP n258), 28 GHz (3GPP n257 and n261), and 39 GHz (3GPP n260) bands [5].

Moreover, as mentioned before, one of the main advantages of 5G is the PHY layer flexibility, which uses different configurations depending on the scope of the application. One of the key parameters to define the 5G waveform is the subcarrier spacing (SCS). SCS is defined from a set of possible numerologies (μ) as follows:

$$SCS(kHz) = 15 \cdot 2^\mu \quad (1)$$

where μ represents numerology and can be 0, 1, 2, 3, or 4. As shown in Table I, the numerology also defines the slot duration and the symbol length. Furthermore, these parameters present the opposite behavior if compared with SCS. That is, the higher the SCS, the shorter the slot and symbol durations.

One of the consequences of using high frequencies is that the Doppler shift is also increased. To avoid a negative impact on the received signal, it is recommended to use high μ configurations ($\mu = 3$ or $\mu = 4$) [17]. These configurations imply that the minimum SCS is 120 kHz and that the symbol time, including the Cyclic Prefix (CP), does not exceed 10 μ s.

As shown in Table I, the numerology also determines the maximum bandwidth that can be used in each case. Except for $\mu = 4$, the maximum number of RBs that can be reserved in the rest of the cases is 275 (for $\mu = 4$, it is 138). The following expression (see [19]) is used to calculate the maximum bandwidth in each case:

$$BW = NRB \cdot BW_{RB} = NRB \cdot 12 \cdot SCS \quad (2)$$

where NRB is the number of RB allocated and BW_{RB} is the bandwidth of a single RB, which is equal to the size of 12 subcarriers separated SCS kHz. Therefore, following the recommended configurations for the mmWave frequency bands, the maximum bandwidths offered are close to 400 MHz. Moreover, in FR2, channels can be aggregated, increasing the overall bandwidth.

Lastly, it should be remarked that the 5G waveform configurations for the mmWave frequency bands have an impact on the RRM process. In particular, as high numerologies have to be used, the symbol time is short, and, consequently, the Transmission Time Intervals (TTIs) are shorter. Therefore, RRM algorithms must guarantee a balance between performance and frequency of execution. For this reason, in general, RRM algorithms can be classified into Fast RRM since they are executed in each TTI, and Slow RRM, which are those that are executed with a lower frequency [20].

B. Propagation Challenges

The propagation channel is a challenge in itself for any wireless communication medium. Most communication systems have been implemented below 6 GHz, and, therefore, there is extensive knowledge. However, in the case of the mmWave frequency bands, some behaviors/effects are different from those assumed so far. Therefore, this section summarizes the main characteristics and differences of the propagation channels of the mmWave frequency bands with respect to traditional microwave systems.

One of the main consequences of the increase in frequency is that the path losses grow considerably. Specifically, taking free space losses as a reference, increasing the frequency by an order of magnitude (i.e., $\times 10$) implies having additional losses of 20 dB. However, since path losses do not depend solely on frequency, there are propagation models for different frequency ranges. Regarding the mmWave frequency bands, the 3GPP TR 38.901 [21] channel model models different path losses depending on the application scenario. Among them, the models Urban Microcells (UMi) and Urban Macrocells (UMa) represent traditional cellular networks, and Indoor Hotspot (InH) and Indoor Factory (InF) are used for different indoor facilities. Fig. 1 shows the evolution of 3GPP TR 38.901 path losses developed in [21] as a function of distance for the UMi and UMa models, assuming Line-of-Sight (LOS) and non-LOS (NLOS), for the 30 GHz band (Fig. 1(a)) and the 60 GHz band (Fig. 1(b)). Furthermore, in [21], the probability of having LOS conditions is also modeled as a function of the scenario. In particular, these probability distributions have a negative exponential trend, and the UMa model has a higher probability of having a LOS condition than the UMi model.

Another vital factor in mmWave frequency bands is that as they have smaller wavelengths than microwaves, they are more sensitive to obstacles [22]. Specifically, according to [23], obstacles in indoor environments or walls show higher penetration losses in the mmWave frequency bands. In addition, when objects are placed between the transmitter and the receiver in the mmWave frequency band communications, the characteristics of the channel vary considerably, and the

TABLE I: Influence of the 5G numerology value over different waveform parameters

μ	SCS (kHz)	#Slot/Subframe	Slot (ms)	OFDM Symbol (μ s)	CP (μ s)	Total Length (μ s)	RB _{MAX}	BW _{MAX} (MHz)
0	15	1	1	66.67	4.69	71.36	275	49.5
1	30	2	0.5	33.33	2.34	35.67	275	99
2	60	4	0.25	16.67	1.17	17.84	275	198
3	120	8	0.125	8.33	0.57	8.90	275	396
4	240	16	0.0625	4.17	0.29	4.46	138	397.44

Fig. 1: Path loss attenuation following 3GPP TR 38.901 for different frequency bands: (a) 30 GHz, (b) 60 GHz.

shadowing effects are very damaging. The deterioration of the signal due to meteorological causes is another effect due to the wavelength size. In particular, when exceeding 10 GHz, hydrometeors (rain or hail) must be taken into account. These effects cause additional attenuations that are modelled as in [24].

C. Benefits & Drawbacks

One of the main benefits of the mmWave frequency bands is the increase in capacity offered because the available bandwidths are much higher than those of sub-6 GHz bands. This effect is reflected in two parameters: the number of users served, and the throughput offered. Specifically, the first parameter is analyzed in more detail in Table II.

To carry out the analysis, two typical bandwidths of 5G communications in the sub-6GHz bands (i.e., 50 and 100 MHz) and two other bandwidths corresponding to the mmWave frequency bands (i.e., 400 MHz and 1 GHz) have been chosen. In addition, since they determine the transmitted throughput, three MCS values have also been selected according to Table 5.1.3.1-2 in [19]: the minimum (i.e., MCS0, QPSK 120/1024), an intermediate one (i.e., MCS14, 64QAM 616/1024) and the maximum (i.e., MCS28, 256QAM 948/1024). Then, in order to contextualize the analysis, three relevant use cases for the future 5G communications with completely different capacity constraints have been used as reference. The first is Internet of Things (IoT), and the characteristics defined in the Rel-13 (Narrow Band IoT) have been taken into account, where a maximum data rate of 200 kbps per user in downlink channels is allowed [25].

The second is the reception of video content in mobile and portable devices, which, according to [26], a minimum data rate of 2 Mbps is required for high-quality video content. Finally, AR/VR applications have been used due to their promising future. In this case, the necessary capacity is usually related to a wide range, where the highest quality applications can reach up to 100 Mbps and the ones of basic qualities between 20 and 30 Mbps [27]. For the analysis, 25 Mbps has been chosen as a potential representative value of the mobile AR/VR applications. As it can be seen in Table II, the increase in bandwidth leads to a proportional increase in the number of users served, which occurs in applications based on mmWave frequency bands. In fact, the number of users served in mmWave frequency band channels present a linear increase in comparison with the sub-6GHz channels regardless of the MCS that is used. In addition, it should be noted that if due to the channel or application conditions, it is necessary to use the most robust MCS, the performance obtained with the channels of the sub-6GHz bands is very limited (e.g., it is not possible to implement AR/VR). In contrast, in the mmWave frequency bands, access to a relevant number of users in each case can be guaranteed.

On the contrary, the main disadvantages of mmWave frequency bands are the consequences derived from the increase in the path losses suffered by the transmissions. Therefore, to compensate more gNBs must be entered in the mmWave frequency bands than in the sub-6GHz bands. For example, taking as a reference a network with a coverage radius of 1km (i.e., an area of 3140 km²) and a central frequency of 2 GHz, if it is assumed that the path loss model that affects it

TABLE II: Analysis of the maximum number of users that could be served using different bandwidth sizes for different applications

MCS	Efficiency	Application	Constraint	Users in 50 MHz	Users in 100 MHz	Users in 400 MHz	Users in 1 GHz
MCS0	0.2344 bps/Hz	NB-IoT	200 kbps	58	117	468	1172
		Mobile HD video	2 Mbps	5	11	46	117
		AR/VR	25 Mbps	0	0	3	9
MCS14	3.6094 bps/Hz	NB-IoT	200 kbps	902	1804	7218	18047
		Mobile HD video	2 Mbps	90	180	721	1804
		AR/VR	25 Mbps	7	14	57	144
MCS28	7.4063 bps/Hz	NB-IoT	200 kbps	1851	3703	14812	37031
		Mobile HD video	2 Mbps	185	370	1481	3703
		AR/VR	25 Mbps	14	29	118	296

is the UMa-LOS shown in Section III-B, the path loss at the edge of the cell is 100 dB. However, if the network is based on 30 GHz transmissions and the same path loss value must be guaranteed, the cell edge is located at 85 meters with an area of 22.7 km². Consequently, the number of gNBs needed to cover that area would be 138 times greater.

Undoubtedly, due to the presented facts, mmWave frequency bands can be considered ideal for creating small networks (e.g., picocells or femtocells) where additional network access should be guaranteed or additional capacity has to be offered.

D. Potential Applications

The increase in the frequency of implementation of 5G services and, as a consequence, the considerable increase in the channel bandwidths used allows challenging applications to be possible. This subsection shows some of the applications that will possibly be implemented in the 5G mmWave frequency bands.

One of the straightforward applications of 5G mmWave frequency bands is to offer traditional broadband applications with considerably enhanced qualities [28]. For example, applications that require high data rates such as AR/VR content, 4k/8k video content, or 360° video streaming may be easier to implement on the mmWave frequency bands.

Another possible application is to use the 5G mmWave frequency bands to guarantee access to content in high-attendance environments [29]. Stadiums, concerts, exhibitions, or festivals are clear examples of locations where the density of users is very high and traditional networks are not always capable of serving all users correctly. Therefore, using the 5G mmWave frequency bands in specific areas with large bandwidths considerably reduces the possibility of network saturation. Furthermore, this alternative could be used in combination with existing small networks or could replace the access networks of certain places.

Finally, the use of the 5G mmWave frequency bands for backhaul applications should be highlighted [30]. Although fiber optic systems have traditionally been used for the wireless network backhaul, the reduction in the coverage area in the mmWave frequency bands and the increase in the number of networks generates an increase in the cost of implementation and scalability that may not be assumable. Therefore, using frequency bands above 6 GHz for the backhaul is a real alternative, and applications like [31] and [32] could be implemented more easily than in the sub-6 GHz frequency

Fig. 2: Representation of the proposed RRM schemes: (a) Model A, (b) Model B, (c) Model C.

bands. In particular, the use of 60 GHz unlicensed bands with LOS conditions for backhaul applications is under study [29].

IV. PROPOSED RRM SCHEMES

As mentioned in [9], pure TDMA and pure NOMA RRM schemes can be considered sub-optimal solutions, and the design of combined TDMA and NOMA RRM solutions should provide better performance rates. The objective of this section is to propose different combined RRM schemes.

In this work, three different RRM schemes are proposed, and Fig. 2 shows the representation of each model. Each model contains three different blocks: broadcast, unicast (I), and unicast (II). It should be noted that the unicast (I) and unicast (II) blocks are a set of resources dedicated to the transmission of unicast services, so each one will be divided into multiple individualized unicast services. The main difference between the three models is the combination of the multiplexing schemes. Model A (see Fig. 2(a)) is based on NOMA, where the Upper Layer (UL) is TDMized to distribute the resources between the broadcast service and one of the unicast blocks. The main benefit of this model is that channel resources are distributed twice, once for the UL and once for the Lower Layer (LL). However, the SNR associated with decoding each of the services will assume a penalty for being a NOMA-based transmission. On the other hand, Model B (see Fig. 2(b)) presents a TDMA scheme where, in the first part, NOMA is applied to multiplex the broadcast service and a block of unicast services with the same number of resources as the broadcast block. In this case, the unicast block (II) is transmitted in single-layer mode, so the required SNR per user will be lower than in Model A, but not all the resources are available. Finally, Model C (see Fig. 2(c)) is also a TDMA model where NOMA has been applied to multiplex the two blocks of unicast content. This model presents the most robust broadcast service; since it is configured in single-layer mode,

Algorithm 1 Common steps of the proposed RRM schemes

```

1: Define:  $l = \Delta_1, \dots, \Delta_L$ . Set of possible ILs;
2: Define:  $t_{ti} = 1, \dots, TTI$ . Set of evaluated TTIs;
3: for  $t_{ti} \leq TTI$  do
4:   Step 1 - CQI acquisition:
        $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_K\}$ 
5:   for  $l \leq \Delta_L$  do
6:     Step 2 - Broadcast service configuration:
        $BW_{BR_l}, eff_{BR_l}, th_{BR_l}$ 
7:     Step 3 - Unicast service configuration in block
(I):
        $[BW_{UN_{1,l}}, eff_{UN_{1,l}}, th_{UN_{1,l}}] \dots$ 
        $[BW_{UN_{N,l}}, eff_{UN_{N,l}}, th_{UN_{N,l}}]$ 
8:     Step 4 - Unicast service configuration in block
(II):
        $[BW_{UN_{N+1,l}}, eff_{UN_{N+1,l}}, th_{UN_{N+1,l}}] \dots$ 
        $[BW_{UN_{N+M,l}}, eff_{UN_{N+M,l}}, th_{UN_{N+M,l}}]$ 
9:   end for
10:  Step 5 - Get the configuration that maximizes
unicast aggregated throughput:
        $\max_l \sum_{i=1}^{N+M} th_{UN_{i,l}}$ 
11: end for

```

its associated SNR is the lowest. However, the use of the spectrum is lower than in the case of Model A.

Algorithm 1 shows a five-step generalization of the RRM schemes presented above. In short, after acquiring the CQI of each user at each TTI (Step 1), the resource allocation is carried out for different Injection Level (IL) values. First, the broadcast service is configured (Step 2) and, then, according to the available amount of RBs and the multiplexing structure, unicast block (I) and unicast block (II) are configured (Steps 3 and 4). Finally, when all the IL configurations are calculated, in Step 5, the best-performing solution is selected.

It should be mentioned that the RRM schemes are designed so that they can be executed for each TTI, and, therefore, the resource allocation is dynamically adapted. The first step consists in obtaining feedback from each user. In this case, the feedback is the CQI (i.e., u_k) perceived by each k^{th} user connected to the gNB. By gathering each feedback, the CQI distribution vector $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_K\}$ is generated, being K the total number of users in the network.

Then, the three steps related to configuring the three service blocks are executed for all the IL values, where $l = \Delta_1, \dots, \Delta_L$ represents the set of possible IL values. In order to set the range of possible ILs, the same range as in ATSC 3.0 has been used [33]. It is composed of 31 values, where steps of 1 dB are used for IL between -25 dB and -5 dB and steps of 0.5 dB between -5 dB and 0 dB. First, the broadcast service is configured in Step 2. To do so, the RRM scheme calculates, according to the minimum broadcast capacity constraint, the required number of resource blocks (BW_{BR_l}). It should be noted that the BW_{BR_l} calculation varies depending on if the broadcast block is configured in single-layer or the UL of

a two-layer system. In particular, in the case of Model C, the BW_{BR_l} calculation is directly carried out with the SNR related with the CQI values. In contrast, in Models A and B, the SNR required to obtain each CQI has to be recalculated since they assume a penalization due to the two-layer structure. The SNR adaptation for the UL has been carried out according to [34]. Then, the throughput of the broadcast service (th_{BR_l}) is calculated as follows:

$$th_{BR_l} = BW_{BR_l} * eff_{BR_l} \quad (3)$$

eff_{BR_l} is the efficiency of the transmitted service (bps/Hz), which is obtained from the selected MCS value according to Table 5.1.3.1-2 in [19].

In Step 3, the first block of the unicast services is configured. In this work, the unicast users are first served starting from the unicast blocks located at the LL. Simulations have shown that this structure gives better results than starting serving unicast users in the UL or single-layer mode. One of the main differences among the RRM models is the RBs dedicated to each unicast service configuration block. Concretely, the three models have a different amount of resources ($BW_{UN(I)}$) in Step 3. In the case of Model A, as the unicast block (I) is extended during the whole bandwidth, the amount of resources is equal to the total amount of RB in the channel (BW_{TOT}). On the contrary, both Model B and Model C have a limited amount of resources. In fact, while in Model B $BW_{UN(I)}$ is equal to BW_{BR} , in Model C is calculated as follows:

$$BW_{UN(I)} = BW_{TOT} - BW_{BR} \quad (4)$$

Once the total number of RBs available for the unicast block (I) has been determined, the RRM scheme begins to serve users one by one. In this case, users are served based on their feedback so that users with better CQIs are managed first. The main reason is that they require fewer RBs than users with bad CQI, and access to a greater number of users can be guaranteed. In order to configure the service to each user, the requested CQI is taken as a reference to decide the number of RBs required for each user ($BW_{UN_{l,k}}$). Then, similar to Eq. (3), the throughput delivered to the k^{th} user using the l^{th} IL is calculated. As in the case of the broadcast service, an SNR adaptation has to be applied since the SNR associated with the requested CQI value has been calculated in single-layer mode, and the unicast services delivered in the first unicast block are organized in the LL. Also in this case, the LL SNR adaptation is based on the procedure defined in [34]. Then, in the first unicast block, the CQI value for the LL is selected to guarantee that the SNR required for the LL is equal to or less than the required in single-layer mode. When the configuration for the k^{th} user is managed, the number of RBs available for unicast block (I) is updated by subtracting the resources allocated to the previous user:

$$BW_{UN(I)} = BW_{UN(I)} - BW_{UN_{l,k}} \quad (5)$$

Then, the algorithm checks if there are available RBs to continue the resource allocation of the first block ($BW_{UN(I)} > 0$). If there are still available RBs, the following user (i.e., $k + 1$) in U is served. If not, the RRM algorithm goes to Step 4.

Fig. 3: Use case representation.

The configuration of the services of the unicast block (II) is similar to the process described in Step 3. In this case, the first user to be served is the user $N + 1$, N being the last user to be served entirely in the unicast block (I). If, on the other hand, the user N has not been fully served in the previous block, before starting to serve $N + 1$, the missing throughput of N is completed. Afterward, the same process as shown in Step 3 is repeated, but taking into account in the SNR adaptation process that the unicast block (II) is not located in the LL. In fact, SNR adaptation is necessary only in Models A and C since the unicast service is transmitted on the UL. In Model B, no adaptation is required because the transmission of the unicast services is carried out in single-layer mode. Once all the resources dedicated to the unicast block (II) are finished ($BW_{UN(II)} \leq 0$), all the user configurations are saved, and the following IL is evaluated (i.e., $l + 1$). At this point, M represents the number of users served in the second unicast block and $N + M$ the total number of unicast users served.

The resource allocation process is repeated until the calculations are completed for all the ILs described in l , and, in the last step (i.e., Step 5), the best performing configuration is selected. In this case, the throughput of the unicast services is determined as the optimization parameter. Therefore, the best performing configuration is determined by looking for the configuration that has the highest aggregate unicast throughput:

$$\max_l \sum_{i=1}^{N+M} th_{UN,i,l} \quad (6)$$

V. EVALUATION USE CASE

A challenging multimedia use case has been chosen to test the RRM schemes shown in the previous section. A crowded museum room is taken as a reference with many potential service requests in a reduced service area. Fig. 3 shows a simplified representation of the use case. The service offered

TABLE III: Use case parameters

Parameter	Value
Center Frequency	28 GHz
Bandwidth	400 MHz
SCS	120 kHz
Tx Power	24 dBm
BS Antenna Height	3 m
RX Antenna Height	1.5 m
LOS/NLOS	LOS
Path Loss	InH model in [21]
User Type	Pedestrians
Number of Users	Up to 320
Speed	3 km/h
Mobility Type	RWP
Hall Size	30m x 30m x 3m
Desired Delay Spread	16 ns
Channel Model	TDL-D, TDL-E
Shadowing	$\sigma = 3$ dB
Noise Power	-90 dBm
Noise Figure	9 dB
RRM Frequency	1 ms
Broadcast Service Capacity	1-10 Mbps
Unicast Service Capacity	3-30 Mbps/user

is a mixed broadcast/unicast mode. The primary content is transmitted on the broadcast service (green dashed line in Fig. 3). Each user inside the museum room will get access to a common online platform where the physical distribution of the room and the list of additional content available is described. Then, the unicast service will convey the customized service requested by each user (red solid line in Fig. 3). This customized content may be video content with supplementary material related to the works of art, AR content to interact with the exhibition, interactive games, etc. The service model requires guaranteed access to the broadcast service to all users and, on-demand content provision to the largest possible number of users.

Broadcast and unicast services have different requirements. The broadcast service will use the lowest possible Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS), MCS0 (QPSK 120/1024) to guarantee that all users in the room have access to the application [19]. In addition, the minimum offered capacity will range between one and ten Mbps, depending on both the type of downloaded content (data, images, video, etc.) and end-user (mobile, tablet, laptop, etc.). In contrast, the unicast personalization service does not have the same strict accessibility requirements. The service will be encoded in coherence with its Channel Quality Indicator (CQI). Regarding the minimum offered capacity to unicast content, a range from three to 30 Mbps will be considered. This capacity range is compatible with services with low requirements (video content to small screen mobile devices) to more demanding services such as AR applications on tablets with large high definition screen displays.

The system simulations have been carried out with OM-Net++ [35]. The simulation environment is a space of 30x30 meters and 3 m height, representing the room where the works of art and service receiver users are concentrated. A transmitter has been placed on the room ceiling (i.e., 3 m transmitter antenna height), and the receivers have been randomly distributed throughout the room. The receivers are pedestrians that move

TABLE IV: Throughput, served unicast users and ADR results of NOMA-only and TDMA-only RRM schemes for different broadcast and unicast service requirements

Minimum Broadcast Service	Minimum Unicast Service	NOMA-only				TDMA-only			
		th_{BR} (Mbps)	th_{UN} (Mbps)	Unicast Users	ADR (Mbps)	th_{BR} (Mbps)	th_{UN} (Mbps)	Unicast Users	ADR (Mbps)
3 Mbps	6 Mbps	92.82	1276.57	202.50	30822.35	3.04	1914.38	293.72	2882.49
	12 Mbps	92.82	1539.29	122.46	31085.07	3.04	2610.01	200.77	3578.12
	24 Mbps	92.82	1545.31	63.00	31091.09	3.04	2835.50	112.05	3803.61
6 Mbps	6 Mbps	92.82	1276.57	202.50	30822.35	6.03	1893.11	290.24	3815.88
	12 Mbps	92.82	1539.29	122.46	31085.07	6.03	2545.45	195.61	4468.22
	24 Mbps	92.82	1545.31	63.00	31091.09	6.03	2741.47	109.98	4664.24

at an average speed of 3 km/h following the Random Waypoint Point (RWP) mobility model [36]. The central frequency used to offer the service is 28 GHz, and a bandwidth of 400 MHz is used to provide broadcast and unicast services to all users. The propagation is modelled with the 3GPP TDL-D and TDL-E (Tapped Delay Line) indoor profiles [21]. Table III summarizes the main features of this models, with a short delay spread of 16 ns and a shadowing effect with a mean zero and σ 3 dB. Finally, the designed RRM algorithms are executed for every subframe (1 ms), so all the RBs contained in a subframe are distributed, during the resource allocation phase.

The rest of the use case parameters are shown in Table III.

VI. RESULTS

This section evaluates the performance of the RRM schemes shown in Section IV for the use case defined in Section V. First, the evaluation metrics are introduced and, then, the results are discussed.

A. Evaluation Metrics

Two parameters are used to describe capacity. The first one is the throughput per service, which is a two-fold parameter that defines the datarate dedicated to the broadcast service and the unicast service. The throughput of the broadcast service (th_{BR}) is calculated in Eq. (3). The objective of the th_{BR} is to show if the RRM algorithm is capable of adjusting the offered capacity to the minimum throughput requirement imposed by the application. In contrast, unicast service throughput (th_{UN}) measures the volume of unicast traffic on the network and is calculated as the sum of all the individual unicast services offered:

$$th_{UN} = \sum_{i=1}^N th_{UN_i} = \sum_{i=1}^N BW_{UN_i} * eff_{UN_i} \quad (7)$$

where, i is the unicast user index, N is the amount of served unicast users, and th_{UN_i} is the individual throughput value of i^{th} unicast user, which is calculated as in (3), but following the bandwidth allocated for each user (BW_{UN_i}) and the efficiency decided for each user (eff_{UN_i}). Then, the other parameter related to the capacity measurement is the Aggregate Data Rate (ADR), representing the sum of all the data received by each user. It is defined as follows:

$$ADR = th_{BR} * \gamma + th_{UN} \quad (8)$$

where, γ represents the number of users able to decode the broadcast service correctly.

Two additional metrics are used to evaluate the algorithm performance in terms of the number of users served. On the one hand, availability will be used as a robustness indicator of the broadcast service. Availability measures the number of users who can receive the common service correctly with respect to the total number of users. Availability must be above 95% to guarantee that users can access the application with reasonable fluency. On the other hand, the number of users that can be served simultaneously with the personalized unicast service will also be measured. In this case, the unicast user number served in each configuration will be presented directly. It should be noted that the personalized service has lower priority, so the number of users that will be given access will be considerably less than in the case of the broadcast service.

B. NOMA-only and TDMA-only modes

This subsection evaluates the performance of RRM schemes based on a single technique (NOMA-only or TDMA-only) in the use case proposed in previous sections. For this, Table IV presents the results obtained in terms of throughput for both services (th_{BR} and th_{UN}), the number of unicast users served, and the ADR.

First, it should be noted that the results of NOMA-only do not adapt to variations in the capacity requirements of the broadcast service. This effect occurs because the entire bandwidth (i.e., 400 MHz) is used for the broadcast service, which is much higher than the requirements established by the use case. On the contrary, variations in the unicast service requirement cause a slight reduction in th_{UN} and a considerable decrease in the number of users served. On the other hand, the TDMA-only algorithm does allow the services offered to be adapted according to the application requirements. For this reason, the th_{BR} adapts to the minimum to offer and allows the th_{UN} and the number of unicast users served to be better than those offered by NOMA-only. Finally, it is necessary to emphasize the difference in the ADR results. NOMA-only offers around ten times more ADR than TDMA-only in all cases. This effect is caused because with NOMA-only, it is not possible to adapt the th_{BR} to the imposed requirements, and the capacity offered is well above what is requested, which causes extremely high ADR values. However, this data is not representative since the difference does not indicate an improvement compared to TDMA-only, but rather a misuse of available resources.

Undoubtedly, these results agree with the conclusions described in [9], where it was previously shown that schemes that

Fig. 4: Availability results of the proposed RRM methods.

use NOMA-only were not capable of adapting to the use case requirements. However, in [9], the mmWave frequency bands were not used, and, therefore, the bandwidths are smaller, which makes the differences between NOMA and TDMA not as evident as in this case. In fact, in sub-6 GHz applications, NOMA still outperforms TDMA. The advantage of NOMA is less clear when larger channel bandwidths are applied. Therefore, the RRM schemes that approach the optimal distribution of resources are those that combine TDMA and NOMA. A joint TDMA-NOMA RRM benefits from the ability of TDMA to adapt to application requirements in combination with the spectral efficiency provided by NOMA.

C. Combined RRM algorithms

The accessibility to the entire set of services depends on the system availability. Fig. 4 shows the availability results for all models with two different UL SNR penalties (0.5 dB and 1 dB). The SNR penalty represents the difference between the minimum SNR required to decode the same configuration in single-layer mode and NOMA. These two penalty values have been chosen to guarantee an acceptable worsen reliability of NOMA systems, as shown in [37]. The variation in the requirements of broadcast and unicast services hardly affects availability, so the values shown in Fig. 4 are average values of all the TTIs. First of all, all the values are above 99%, so that they are all valid results since they are above the 95% threshold defined in Section VI-A. Among all the models, as expected, the one that offers the best availability is Model C. This advantage comes from the fact that the broadcast service operates in SL mode, it has lower SNR requirements than Models A and B, and is not influenced by the UL SNR penalty. However, the difference between models with penalty (i.e., A and B) and Model C is slight and assumable. Also, as expected, availability improves on Models A and B by reducing the UL SNR penalty. Based on the above-shown results, a UL SNR penalty of 1 dB will be used in the rest of the results since it has a similar availability rate to 0.5 dB.

The number of unicast users served is shown in Fig. 5 for three different broadcast service requirements: three Mbps

(see Fig. 5(a)), six Mbps (see Fig. 5(b)) and nine Mbps (see Fig. 5(c)). Models A and C are once again the ones with the best performance, with very similar results. Regarding the service requirements, the required minimum broadcast capacity requirement hardly interferes with the results. In contrast, the minimum unicast service requirement does have an impact on the number of users served, especially in Model B, which is the one that decreases the most rapidly. If the requirements of unicast services are related to real personalization services, services related to video applications would be below ten Mbps, while those oriented to AR applications between 20 and 30 Mbps. In the case of videos with Models A and C, practically all users could receive them (minimum 300 users), while with Model B, the service could be guaranteed to about 250 users. On the contrary, for AR-based applications, Models A and C show that they can serve 50% more users since they guarantee access to around 150 users, while with Model B, it would not reach 100 users.

Table V shows the throughput results per service obtained with each of the RRM models for different broadcast and unicast requirements. The th_{BR} obtained in all cases is adjusted to the minimum required by the application, unlike the NOMA cases shown in the previous subsection. Also, the th_{UN} shows a remarkable increase as the minimum unicast throughput per user increases. On the contrary, when increasing the broadcast service requirement, the th_{UN} presents a slight reduction. This effect indicates that the RBs reserved to cover the broadcast service are very few compared to those that remain to serve the unicast users and, therefore, it hardly affects the results. Model B offers a much lower th_{UN} than Models A and C. Looking at the configuration with the most significant difference (minimum broadcast service 3 Mbps and minimum unicast service 24 Mbps), Models A and C improve the performance of Model B by almost 60%. The best results are found for Model A, with th_{UN} values slightly higher than Model C, up to 4% better in some cases.

Fig. 6 shows the ADR results for each RRM model, with minimum broadcast service bitrates of 3 Mbps, 6 Mbps, and 9 Mbps illustrated in Fig. 6(a), Fig. 6(b), and Fig. 6(c), respectively. As in the throughput case, the ADR results also show that Model B has a significantly lower performance than Models A and C. However, the difference between the models is lower. The performance difference between Model A and Model B in Fig. 6 (a) is close to 30%, while in the case of Fig. 6 (c) it does not exceed 22%. Likewise, the difference in performance between Models A and C also increases as the requirement for broadcast service grows, indicating that Model A always offers the best ADR result. The different trends shown by the curves should also be highlighted since they have, first, a phase of exponential increase and, then, a saturation phase. The exponential increase occurs because increasing the unicast service requirement does not imply a linear decrease in the number of users. In fact, as explained in Section IV, by serving the users with the best conditions first, the first users who are left out of the personalization service are the users who require more RBs, since they request low MCS values. Therefore, as the unicast service requirement increases, the services' efficiency increases and the ADR grows.

Fig. 5: Number of served unicast users for different minimum broadcast capacity values: (a) 3 Mbps, (b) 6 Mbps, (c) 9 Mbps.

TABLE V: Obtained throughput per service results for different broadcast and unicast requirements

Minimum Broadcast Service	Minimum Unicast Service	Model A		Model B		Model C	
		th_{BR} (Mbps)	th_{UN} (Mbps)	th_{BR} (Mbps)	th_{UN} (Mbps)	th_{BR} (Mbps)	th_{UN} (Mbps)
3 Mbps	6 Mbps	3.04	2041.48	3.04	1920.58	3.04	2038.11
	12 Mbps	3.04	3500.97	3.04	2645.89	3.04	3493.16
	24 Mbps	3.04	4630.19	3.04	2896.99	3.04	4570.80
6 Mbps	6 Mbps	6.03	2025.62	6.03	1904.30	6.03	2020.03
	12 Mbps	6.03	3483.70	6.03	2614.94	6.03	3467.22
	24 Mbps	6.03	4543.06	6.03	2870.12	6.03	4423.98
9 Mbps	6 Mbps	9.03	2011.39	9.03	1887.28	9.03	2004.64
	12 Mbps	9.03	3465.86	9.03	2584.45	9.03	3439.82
	24 Mbps	9.03	4455.26	9.03	2835.19	9.03	4275.34

Fig. 6: ADR results for different minimum broadcast capacity values: (a) 3 Mbps, (b) 6 Mbps, (c) 9 Mbps.

On the contrary, in the saturation phase, this effect does not occur. In saturation, the users with the worst conditions have already been rejected, and those who are served have good channel conditions, so the increase in the minimum unicast service practically implies a linear reduction in the number of users served. Finally, it is worth highlighting the ADR result obtained for Models A and C between three and six Mbps of unicast service. In those cases, despite increasing the unicast service, the ADR hardly changes. In the case of three Mbps, all users are served once, and the RRM model performs a second round in serving the majority of users during the same TTI. As the requirement of the unicast service increases, the users that are left out are those that had been served a second time, that is, those with good channel condition. Consequently, the total spectral efficiency falls, and the ADR does not grow. This effect does not occur in Model B because it presents a less

efficient use of resources, and it does not serve as many users in the second round as Models A and C. Therefore, the effect is less noticeable and does not present such an abrupt change in the behavior. However, it can be seen that in Model B, the increase from three to six Mbps is less than the increase from six to nine Mbps.

Finally, when comparing the results shown in this subsection with those obtained with the NOMA-only and TDMA-only schemes (see Section VI-B), it can be seen that Models A and C improve all KPIs and that Model B is slightly better. Specifically, both Model A and Model C improve the results shown in Table IV by around 50%. Especially, the difference increases when the requirements of broadcast and unicast services increase. Therefore, as a summary, it should be noted that the RRM schemes that combine TDMA and NOMA considerably improve the performance of the simple models

and that, in particular, Models A and C are the best possible options.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This article considers resource allocation techniques that combine TDMA and NOMA to improve spectral efficiency in applications implemented in the mmWave frequency bands. For this, three different RRM models have been designed and evaluated in terms of throughput (th_{BR} and th_{UN}), capacity (number of unicast users served), and availability. In addition, they have been compared to schemes that only implement one of the multiplexing mechanisms (only-NOMA and only-TDMA). Moreover, the main challenges and possible applications of 5G in the mmWave frequency bands have also been highlighted, and an innovative use case has been designed to test the designed RRM schemes.

Regarding the results, it has been verified that the RRM schemes that combine TDMA and NOMA considerably improve the schemes of a single multiplexing mechanism. Especially when the application requirements are high, the difference in performance exceeds 50%. Concerning the RRM models designed, it should be noted that even Model B has acceptable performance, Models A and C outperform Model B in all KPIs. Furthermore, the results indicate that for the proposed use case, using Models A and C, in the case of additional high-quality videos, access to the personalization service can be guaranteed to around 300 users (almost all the users in the cell). In contrast, in AR services, a minimum of 150 users is guaranteed with Models A and C. Finally, it should be highlighted that Model A outperforms Model C slightly since Model A downgrades less the results when the broadcast and unicast requirements are increased.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cisco Visual Networking Index: Global Mobile Data Traffic Forecast Update, 2017-2022.
- [2] ITU-R Rec. ITU-R M. 2083-0, "IMT Vision — Framework and Overall Objectives of the Future Development of IMT for 2020 and Beyond," Sept. 2015.
- [3] ITU-R Rec. ITU-R M. 2410-0, "Minimum requirements related to technical performance for IMT-2020 radio interface(s)," Nov. 2017.
- [4] 3GPP TS 38.201 v15.0.0, Tech. Spec. Group Services and System Aspects, "NR; Physical layer; General description," Tech. Rep., Jan. 2018.
- [5] A. V. Lopez, A. Chervyakov, G. Chance, S. Verma, and Y. Tang, "Opportunities and challenges of mmwave nr," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 4–6, 2019.
- [6] L. Zhang, W. Li, Y. Wu, X. Wang, S.-I. Park, H. M. Kim, J.-Y. Lee, P. Angueira, and J. Montalban, "Layered-division-multiplexing: Theory and practice," *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 216–232, 2016.
- [7] J. Montalban, P. Scopelliti, M. Fadda, E. Iradier, C. Desogus, P. Angueira, M. Murrioni, and G. Araniti, "Multimedia multicast services in 5g networks: Subgrouping and non-orthogonal multiple access techniques," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 91–95, 2018.
- [8] E. Iradier, J. Montalban, L. Fanari, P. Angueira, L. Zhang, Y. Wu, and W. Li, "Using noma for enabling broadcast/unicast convergence in 5g networks," *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, vol. 66, no. 2, pp. 503–514, 2020.
- [9] E. Iradier, A. Abuin, L. Fanari, J. Montalban, P. Angueira, L. Zhang, W. Li, and Y. Wu, "Broadcast/unicast convergence in noma-based 5g: a rrm optimization algorithm," in *2020 IEEE International Symposium on Broadband Multimedia Systems and Broadcasting (BMSB)*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [10] S. Scott-Hayward and E. Garcia-Palacios, "Multimedia resource allocation in mmwave 5g networks," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 240–247, 2015.
- [11] A. Samuylov, D. Moltchanov, R. Kovalchukov, R. Pirmagomedov, Y. Gaidamaka, S. Andreev, Y. Koucheryavy, and K. Samouylov, "Characterizing resource allocation trade-offs in 5g nr serving multicast and unicast traffic," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 3421–3434, 2020.
- [12] R. Liu, Q. Chen, G. Yu, and G. Y. Li, "Joint user association and resource allocation for multi-band millimeter-wave heterogeneous networks," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 67, no. 12, pp. 8502–8516, 2019.
- [13] J. Deng, O. Tirkkonen, R. Freij-Hollanti, T. Chen, and N. Nikaein, "Resource allocation and interference management for opportunistic relaying in integrated mmwave/sub-6 ghz 5g networks," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 94–101, 2017.
- [14] N. Nouri, J. Abouei, M. Jaseemuddin, and A. Anpalagan, "Joint access and resource allocation in ultradense mmwave noma networks with mobile edge computing," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1531–1547, 2019.
- [15] Z. Shi, Y. Wang, L. Huang, and T. Wang, "Dynamic resource allocation in mmwave unified access and backhaul network," in *2015 IEEE 26th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor, and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 2260–2264.
- [16] S. Kumar, S. Suman, and S. De, "Dynamic resource allocation in uav-enabled mmwave communication networks," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2020.
- [17] A. A. Zaidi, R. Baldemair, V. Molés-Cases, N. He, K. Werner, and A. Cedergren, "Ofdm numerology design for 5g new radio to support iot, embb, and mbsfn," *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 78–83, 2018.
- [18] C. K. Agubor, I. Akwukwuegbu, M. Olubiwe, C. O. Nosiri, A. Ehinomen, A. A. Olukunle, S. O. Okozi, L. Ezema, and B. C. Okeke, "A comprehensive review on the feasibility and challenges of millimeter wave in emerging 5g mobile communication," *Adv. Sci. Technol. Eng. Syst.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 138–144, 2019.
- [19] 3GPP TS 38.214 v15.3.0, Tech. Spec. Group Services and System Aspects, "NR; Physical layer procedures for data (Release 15)," Tech. Rep., Sept. 2018.
- [20] Y. Li, E. Pateromichelakis, N. Vucic, J. Luo, W. Xu, and G. Caire, "Radio resource management considerations for 5g millimeter wave backhaul and access networks," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 86–92, 2017.
- [21] 3GPP TR 38.901, Radio Access Network Working Group and others, "Study on channel model for frequencies from 0.5 to 100 ghz (release 15)," Tech. Rep., 2018.
- [22] T. S. Rappaport, Y. Xing, G. R. MacCartney, A. F. Molisch, E. Mellios, and J. Zhang, "Overview of millimeter wave communications for fifth-generation (5g) wireless networks—with a focus on propagation models," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 65, no. 12, pp. 6213–6230, 2017.
- [23] S. Sun, T. S. Rappaport, M. Shafi, P. Tang, J. Zhang, and P. J. Smith, "Propagation models and performance evaluation for 5g millimeter-wave bands," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 67, no. 9, pp. 8422–8439, 2018.
- [24] ITU-R, "Specific attenuation model for rain for use in prediction methods, propagation in non-ionized media," Tech. Rep. P.838-3, 2005.
- [25] S. Persia and L. Rea, "Next generation m2m cellular networks: Lte-mtc and nb-iot capacity analysis for smart grids applications," in *2016 AEIT International Annual Conference (AEIT)*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [26] X. Xu, J. Liu, and X. Tao, "Mobile edge computing enhanced adaptive bitrate video delivery with joint cache and radio resource allocation," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 16406–16415, 2017.
- [27] M. S. Elbamby, C. Perfecto, M. Bennis, and K. Doppler, "Toward low-latency and ultra-reliable virtual reality," *IEEE Network*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 78–84, 2018.
- [28] K. Sakaguchi, T. Haustein, S. Barbarossa, E. C. Strinati, A. Clemente, G. Destino, A. Pärssinen, I. Kim, H. Chung, J. Kim *et al.*, "Where, when, and how mmwave is used in 5g and beyond," *IEICE Transactions on Electronics*, vol. 100, no. 10, pp. 790–808, 2017.
- [29] L. Wei, R. Q. Hu, Y. Qian, and G. Wu, "Key elements to enable millimeter wave communications for 5g wireless systems," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 136–143, 2014.
- [30] Y. Niu, Y. Li, D. Jin, L. Su, and A. V. Vasilakos, "A survey of millimeter wave communications (mmwave) for 5g: opportunities and challenges," *Wireless networks*, vol. 21, no. 8, pp. 2657–2676, 2015.

- [31] L. Zhang, W. Li, Y. Wu, S. Lafleche, Z. Hong, S.-I. Park, J.-Y. Lee, H.-M. Kim, N. Hur, E. Iradier *et al.*, "Using layered division multiplexing for wireless in-band distribution links in next generation broadcast systems," *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 68–82, 2020.
- [32] W. Li, L. Zhang, Y. Wu, Z. Hong, S. Laffèche, S.-I. Park, S. Kown, S. Ahn, N. Hur, E. Iradier, I. Bilbao, J. Montalban, and P. Angueira, "Integrated inter-tower wireless communications network for terrestrial broadcasting and multicasting systems," *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, vol. 67, no. 3, 2021.
- [33] Advanced Television Systems Committee and others, "ATSC Standard: Physical Layer Protocol (A/322). Doc. A/322: 2106," *Washington, DC, USA*, 2016.
- [34] J. Montalbán, L. Zhang, U. Gil, Y. Wu, I. Angulo, K. Salehian, S.-I. Park, B. Rong, W. Li, H. M. Kim *et al.*, "Cloud transmission: System performance and application scenarios," *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 170–184, 2014.
- [35] A. Varga and R. Hornig, "An overview of the OMNeT++ simulation environment," in *Proceedings of the 1st international conference on Simulation tools and techniques for communications, networks and systems & workshops*. ICST (Institute for Computer Sciences, Social-Informatics and Telecommunications Engineering, 2008, p. 60.
- [36] E. Hyttiä, H. Koskinen, P. E. Lassila, A. Penttinen, J. T. Virtamo, and J. Roszik, "Random waypoint model in wireless networks," 2005.
- [37] E. Iradier, A. Abuin, L. Fanari, J. Montalban, and P. Angueira, "Throughput, capacity and latency analysis of p-noma rrm schemes in 5g urllc," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, pp. 1–23, 2021.